

ELUCIDATION OF THE ETHNIC COMPOSITION OF THE INHABITANTS OF THE JIZZAKH OASIS IN THE HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE

Qakhramon Almanov Obloqulovich

Gulistan State University, 120100. Sirdarya Region,

Gulistan City, 4th District, Uzbekistan

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Annotation. This article focuses on the study of toponomical research in Uzbekistan and its surrounding regions. The research examines the ethnic history, place names (toponyms), and their ethnic origins in the Jizzakh oasis and other areas of Uzbekistan. The scientific studies conducted after independence are mainly based on archaeological findings, written sources, ethnographic research, and materials in Turkic, Sogdian, Arabic, and Persian languages. Researchers identified the historical toponymy of the region by studying the settlement of different ethnic groups and tribes, their language, culture, and history. The article presents scientific works aimed at analyzing the toponyms and ethnotoponyms of the Jizzakh oasis, highlighting similarities and differences between ethnic groups.

Keywords. Jizzakh oasis, ethnotoponyms, toponomastics, ethnic history, Turkic toponyms, Sogdian toponyms, archaeology, written sources, regional research, ethnic composition, the Middle Ages, Zarafshan oasis, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, ethnological studies.

A certain part of the research devoted to the study of the ethnic history of the peoples of Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, through toponomic data, is the research carried out in the years after the independence of our country. It is worth noting that in the research conducted during this period, mainly by relying on primary written sources written in Sogdian, Turkish, Chinese, Arabic-Persian and other languages, archaeological finds, as well as Sogdian-language documents and numismatic materials. study made it possible to deeply analyze the history of the peoples of the region.

It is especially noteworthy that such sources are involved in the history of the country. U.Tuychiyev, A.Qayumov, S.Karayev, Kh.Khasanov, E.Murzayev, who have been conducting research for many years on the historical toponomy of our region, including the composition of the population of the Jizzakh oasis, toponyms, especially ethnotoponyms, K.Hakimov, P.Gulomov, I.Karimov, M.Pardayev, B.Tuychiboev, Kh.Khashkirli, G.Boboyorov, A.Zokirov, M.Mirakmalov, T.Salimov, G.Normuradova, A.Togayev, A.Bababekov, J.Alibekov,

Kh.Almanov, A.Pardayev, B.Mirkamilov, A.Bazarbayev, B.Orinboyev's articles and monographs, we witness new interpretations of the country's history.

In particular, the research carried out by S.Khorayev and K.Hakimov on the toponyms of the oasis is distinguished by its extensiveness and consistency [1]. It is observed that some attention is paid to the ethnotoponyms of Jizzakh oasis [2]. The researchers' good knowledge of oasis toponyms and ethnotoponymy, in particular, U.Tuychiyev collected primary data on hundreds of settlements in the Samarkand region and scientifically analyzed them. Most of the place names in the region were in the oasis in the late 19th - early 20th centuries. It is noteworthy to determine that it goes back to the existing ethnonyms.

Looking at the researches of this researcher, we can see that during this period, the ethnotoponyms of the Jizzakh oasis were similar or close to the mountain districts of the Samarkand region, the regions bordering the Jizzakh oasis. When looking at the composition of the population and their location in the territories of the Jizzakh oasis, it is observed that the settlements of the population speaking Kipchak, Kharluk, and Oghuz dialects are located separately. The reason for the location of such a population is probably related to the arrival of the population to the region at different times.

In the researches of Kh.Hakimov, it was noted that the majority of oasis toponyms are Sugdian, Persian, and Turkic toponyms, while in "Annotated dictionary of toponyms of Jizzakh region" by B. Orinboyev, the largest part of oasis toponyms are Turkic and Sugdian based toponyms. It is observed that it is the majority [3]. The scientific works of the local historians and archaeologists A.Gritsina, M.Pardayev, A.Pardayev, A.Raimkulov, B.Tuychiboev, Kh.Almanov, F.Toshboyev, who studied the history of the peoples of the oasis through archaeological objects and written sources, are the works of the Jizzakh oasis. It is of great importance in illuminating its historical geography. Although the main focus of the researchers' scientific research is on the pre-Islamic period of the Jizzakh oasis, it is distinguished by the fact that it gives certain ideas about the toponymy of the oasis.

M.Isakov[4], A.Gritsina[5], M.Pardayev, A.Pardayev's[6] comparing the ancient Jizzakh oasis with the names of the places preserved today from the information in Arabic-Persian language sources related to the Middle Ages. The researchers who focused on the issue of the geographical location of historical toponyms, the etymology of place names, followed the archaeological research of their colleagues who conducted research in the oasis before them. It can be

seen that it works based on the results of excavations[7]. This has had a great impact on the success of scientific research carried out by researchers.

One of the successful researches in the years of independence belongs to the historian and orientalist Sh.Kamoliddin. In his scientific research, the researcher mainly based on the works of Arab geographers and compared them with archaeological materials. In the monograph "Ancient Turkic toponyms of Central Asia" devoted to the ancient Turkic toponymy of the region, hundreds of place names were considered, and the researcher identified a significant part of the toponyms in written sources in Arabic-Persian, Chinese and other languages of the developed Middle Ages as Turkic places. determined that the names form[8]. Oriental scholar in this scientific study of Sh.Kamoliddin, he briefly touched on the historical toponyms of the Jizzakh oasis and showed that an important part of the toponyms of the oasis was formed on the basis of the Turkic language.

In the research of G.Boboyorov, who conducted research on Turkish toponyms in the same region, it is emphasized that there are many toponyms of Turkish origin in the region [9]. At the same time, in the research of Sh.Kamaliddin it is quite controversial how many of them try to associate it with the Turkish language even though it is not originally Turkish. For example, the analysis of place names ending with the topoformants -gon, -khan on the Turkish basis is quite controversial [10].

In recent years, A.Malikov, one of the researchers who conducted ethnological research on Samarkand, which is part of the Zarafshan oasis, and the neighboring Jizzakh oasis, has a significant scientific research. Similarly, the researches of A.Togaev, who conducted research in the Forish region of the oasis, and the researches of A. Bababekov, who conducted field ethnographic research in the Sangzor-Zomin region, are also important for the study of ethnotoponyms of the oasis [11]. Also, F.S.Tolipov, A.Pardaev, A.Bazarbaev, F.Akchaev, Kh.Almanov, who conducted research on the ethnic composition of the oasis population, have been contributing to the study of the country's history in one way or another. According to the researcher A.Malikov, the ethnic group that existed in the Zarafshan oasis and its neighboring areas of Jizzakh in the late 19th - early 20th centuries during the study of the situation, the Uzbek tribes in the oasis, such as Yuz, Kungyrot, Nayman, Saray, Kipchak, Turkmen ("Nurota Turkmen" or "Uzbek-Turkmen") published a number of scientific articles [12].

Researcher A.Malikov ethnologically analyzed the composition of 92 Uzbek seeds in his research, and approached the small seeds and balls (horns)

contained in each seed based on a deep analysis, based on the distribution areas of these seeds. illuminates.

The researcher pays special attention to ethnonyms related to the Kazakh, Karakalpak and other Turkic ethnic groups in the oasis. In A.Malikov's scientific monograph "Turkish ethnonyms and ethnotoponyms of the Zarafshan Valley (XVIII - early XX centuries)", he mentions more than 300 Turkish ethnotoponyms in the oasis and explains them by name [13]. It is noteworthy that T.Salimov, A.Tagayev, A.Bababekov, who conducted research on the ethnic composition of the oasis population, expressed their attitude to such issues.

Especially B.Tuychiboev and Kh.Kashkirli in their monograph "Language of Zomin" which is the product of their many years of scientific research briefly touched on the ethnic units of the population of the oasis, the clans in these areas and the different groups in their composition. p and have expressed a number of their thoughts and opinions to branches [14]. F.Akchaev's research on the history of shrines in the oasis, which plays an important role in the religious views of the inhabitants of the Jizzakh oasis, also stands out in the study of the spiritual life of the inhabitants [15]. In the research of G.Normuradova, who studied the social stratification of the population of Samarkand region at the end of the 19th - beginning of the 20th century, the social status of the population in the oasis was also analyzed [16], A.Malikov, U.Tuychiyev, B.Tuychiboev, Kh.Kashqirli, A.Tagayev, We must emphasize that the researches of A.Bababekov, Kh.Almanov, A.Pardayev are the most consistent and perfect among other researches carried out on this topic.

A.Malikov as a result of studying the ethnotoponyms of the Zarafshan oasis, the main attention is paid to the ethnotoponyms existing in the oasis, and they are comparatively analyzed. In his research, several clans and tribes living in the Jizzakh oasis meet with different clans living in the Zarafshan oasis in a situation where they have the same ethnic origin. based on his point of view, he makes a short comparative analysis of such issues. We can say that our research is a logical continuation of A.Malikov's research conducted in Zarafshan oasis in another area. While A.Malikov's research focused on the ethnonyms that are the basis of toponyms in the Zarafshan oasis, we focus our attention on the internal network names and ethnotoponyms of clans in the Jizzakh oasis and its territories. We will also try to clarify ethnotoponyms in the oasis we are studying.

For example, the ethno toponyms studied by different researchers in the oasis are considered as a single integrated region without being divided into

regions, i.e. not divided into a number of districts in the oasis (Bakhmal, Zomin, Forish, Gallaorol, Yangiabad). Based on the naming, some of these are ethnotoponyms, patronymics, oronyms, oikonyms during the analysis of various written sources about the etymology of these names. A number of opinions have been put forward regarding the fact that it is an ethnotonym, most of which is found as the name of one of the Uzbek clans, but no consensus has been reached [17].

At this point, although the researches of the above researchers did not cover the entire Jizzakh oasis, according to the nature of its content, the field is written in an ethnographic direction and is rich in a number of different ideas that will help our research. A number of ethnologists, in particular, researchers such as U.Tuychiev, A.Khayumov, O.Buriev, M.Usmonov, S.Tursunov, Sh.Eshonkulov, focused on the ethnic situation in the southern and central regions of Uzbekistan. if[18], several dozens of terms cited in the scientific research of these researchers (oikonym, ethnonym, ethnotonym, patronymics, oronyms, etc.) we should mention that some place names in the Jizzakh region served as an assistant in determining the issue of ethnotonymy or giving another meaning. We should emphasize that Zarafshan, the southern neighbor of the Jizzakh oasis, and Kashkadarya oasis are close to each other, so a large part of the ethnotoponyms in these regions have a very close similarity with the ethnotonymy of the area we are studying[19].

In particular, dozens of ethnotoponyms related to the Uzbek clans of Kungirov, Barlos, Yuz, and Saray in the mountainous districts and surroundings of Samarkand, as well as Chiraqi, Khamashi in the Kashkadarya oasis, and the mountainous districts of the oasis [20] Jizzakh and Zarafshan regions. Also, settlements of the population associated with several clan names such as Naiman, Balkhi, Uyshun, Khushchi, Min, Kirk, Barlos, Karakalpok can be found in the oases we are studying and the oases of Zarafshan, Kashkadarya, and Surhan on its southern side.

Also, a number of researchers have conducted their scientific research on the toponyms of the Nurota mountain range, which is considered a component of the Jizzakh oasis, and its surroundings.

Research scientist G. Boboyorov, in his research on the ethno-political situation of Central Asia in the territory of Uzbekistan in the early Middle Ages based on written sources and numismatic materials, it is noticeable that he paid a lot of attention to Sughd, Ustrushona and Choch oasis [21]. Basically, the Turkic Khanate, especially during the period of its western wing, in its research

on the ancient Turkish coins minted in Ustrushona and Sughd, Ferghana and Choch, emphasizes the occurrence of a number of Turkish titles on Ustrushona coins as well[22]. In particular, according to G.Boboyorov, who identified the occurrence of ancient Turkic titles and epithets such as "Satachari", "Rakhanch", Chirdmish, Panch, "Khotun", "Bilga" in the Sugdian script on the coins of Ustrushona, the toponym "Turon" on the coins of Samarkand place is closely related to the ethno-political realities of the early Middle Ages, and Ustrushona coins have Turkish names coins associated with the title of eltabar are found[23].

According to G.Boboyorov, in the VI-VIII centuries, the status of Turkic ethnic groups increased in all aspects in the vicinity of Sughd, which is evidenced by the establishment of Turkish and Turkic-Sugdian mixed dynasties in Ustrushona, Panch, Kabuduyan, Nakhlahz and Bukhara[24]. In particular, the discovery of many coins minted in Ustrushona in the VII-VIII centuries with the names of rulers with Turkic names and titles, such as Karabogra, Harabugro, confirms this opinion [25].

Our archaeologists A.Berdimurodov, A.Raimkulov, M.Pardayev, who are representatives of the Samarkand School of Archaeology, and a number of other scientists have carried out several scientific works that greatly help in studying the toponymy of the oasis. In particular, in a number of scientific studies by A.Raimkulov and M.Pardayev, he paid attention to issues such as the location, naming, archeological findings, and the place in the life of the oasis of dozens of ancient settlements in the Jizzakh oasis[26]. Similarly, the research of researcher A.Pardayev, who carried out a number of scientific works on the ethnic composition of the oasis population, also plays an important role in the study of the ethnic composition and ethnotoponyms of the oasis population. in his research[27]. Another researcher, B.Mirkamilov, in several of his scientific articles, with a number of opinions, some places in Forish district briefly touching on the names and expressing his thoughts[28]. The opinions and comments of the researchers are of great importance in the study and research of the ethnic history and ethnotoponymy of the oasis.

So, after briefly familiarizing ourselves with the research conducted after the independence of our country, we will conclude that a number of scientific studies have been carried out within the framework of this topic, and certain achievements have been made. included in In particular, the historical significance of the toponyms of the Jizzakh oasis is highlighted, based on the analysis of socio-political and ethno-cultural processes that took place in the

oasis for almost two thousand years, the reasons and factors that played the main role in the ethnic formation of the population of the country today are shown.

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